

Pilot Evaluation Summary	
Intervention Developer	Kinship
Delivery Organisations	Kinship
Evaluator	Ecorys and the University of Exeter
Principal Investigator	James Whitley (Ecorys)
Protocol Author(s)	Dr Freyja Fischer, James Whitley (Ecorys) and Professor Mark Kelson (University of Exeter)
Pilot Intervention Recipients	Kinship carers and the children they look after
Pilot Evaluation Participants	Treatment group: 60 young people whose kinship carers receive support from Kinship Connected Comparator group: 60 young people who are cared for by kinship carers, but whose kinship carers do not receive support from Kinship Connected
Number of Pilot Sites	Estimated five local authorities
Protocol Date	1 March 2023
Version	1

Summary

This document outlines a pilot Randomised Controlled Trial (RCT) of Kinship Connected. Kinship Connected is an intervention for kinship carers of children aged 0-18 years. While previous research has shown a positive impact of Kinship Connected on carers' outcomes, quantitative research on the impact of the intervention on children has not been investigated to date.

The pilot RCT is designed to determine whether a full scale RCT can be conducted on the question "Does the Kinship Connected intervention improve children's mental health outcomes?"

We expect the pilot RCT to take approximately three years, comprising:

- Set up, ethical approval and recruitment: Six to 12 months
- Survey: 24 months (rolling)
- Analysis and reporting: Six months.

Background and problem statement

Kinship care is where a person connected to a child, usually a family member or close friend, looks after the child full-time as their parents cannot. Kinship care is common and increasing. There is estimated to be around 200,000 children living in kinship care in the UK (Kinship 2021); more than double the number of children in local authority care (Kinship 2022).

Kinship care is a complex family form that has not received the same levels of research, funding, or support as other care options for children who are unable to live with their parents, such as foster care and adoption (Wellard et al. 2017, Hunt 2019, Hunt 2020). Kinship carers often have additional vulnerabilities and needs when compared to parents, adoptive parents, and foster carers (Aldgate and McIntosh 2005, Farmer and Moyers 2008, Nandy et al. 2011, Selwyn et al. 2013, Wijedasa 2017, Hunt 2020).

Research has shown that the support offered to carers of vulnerable children has a direct impact on the outcomes for the children; and when they receive inadequate support, they commonly find the parenting role more challenging (McSherry et al. 2016, Neil et al. 2018). The additional needs of the children, combined with the vulnerabilities of their kinship carers, means that kinship carers particularly benefit from additional support (Saunders and Selwyn 2009, Selwyn et al. 2013, Wade et al. 2014, Wellard et al. 2017, Hunt 2018, Hunt 2020). However, it is consistently found that kinship carers and their children either receive insufficient support or no support at all (Hunt and Waterhouse 2012, Selwyn et al. 2013, Wellard et al. 2017, Grandparents Plus 2018, 2019, 2020, Kinship 2021).

There is evidence that additional support can achieve positive outcomes for children cared for by kinship carers (Schofield and Beek 2005, Crittenden 2012, Bifulco and Thomas 2013, McSherry, et al. 2016, Hunt 2020). However, this evidence rarely links to mental health outcomes, particularly of the children cared for.

Kinship Connected is an evidence-informed intensive support programme for kinship carers of children aged 0-18 years old. Specialist project workers provide practical and emotional one-to-one support for up to six months, and beyond if there is a real need for further support. Support can include advocacy, active listening, helping kinship carers access local and national grants, signposting to other agencies, family events, priority access to Kinship's advice line, confidence-building and skills development. As of February 2023, Kinship Connected is currently running in 18 local authorities.

Evidence of Kinship Connected's impact on kinship carers has been acknowledged by independent research (York Consulting 2017, Starks 2018, Starks and Whitley 2020, MacAlister 2022). However, to date there has been little primary research on the impact of kinship care on UK children more generally (Winokur et al, 2014) and no research into Kinship Connected's impact on children's and young people's outcomes.

There is likely to be considerable interest in this research. The positive results of support services for kinship carers provide a solid basis for wider uptake, and there has been further attention to this area following the independent review of children's social care (MacAlister 2022). There is interest in building a robust case for investment in effective approaches to children's social care, including kinship care, in securing better outcomes for children. There is the potential for multi-million pounds of savings to central government from placing children from local authority care into kinship care, resulting from improved health and educational outcomes, and reduced homelessness, crime and anti-social behaviour (Nicol Economics 2020, Starks and Whitley 2020).

We have conducted a **feasibility study** to understand the barriers and facilitators to recruitment of potential participants taking part in a pilot RCT and for the success of the study more generally, what the key outcomes of a pilot impact evaluation should be, how data collection is best managed, and acceptability of randomisation for a full RCT.

Building on this feasibility study, this protocol describes a pilot RCT that is designed to investigate whether it is possible to conduct a full-scale RCT on the research question: “Does the Kinship Connected intervention improve children’s mental health outcomes?”

An RCT offers a higher standard of evidence than previous research into kinship care, offering Level 5 on the Maryland Scientific Methods Scale (Sherman, et al., 1998). The pilot RCT is intended to support the eventual development of a full-scale RCT aimed at demonstrating the effectiveness of the intervention. It will also provide transferable learning for mental health services in dealing with children in kinship, adoptive and foster care.

Intervention and Theory of Change

Table 1 illustrates the Template for Intervention Description and Replication (TIDieR)¹ checklist (Hoffman et al. 2014) for Kinship Connected.

Table 1: TIDieR framework for the description of the intervention

TIDieR item	Response
Brief name <i>Provide the name or a phrase that describes the intervention.</i>	Kinship Connected is an intervention for kinship carers of children aged 0-18 years old, regardless of background or legal status. It is delivered through a hybrid of face-to-face and virtually, determined by the needs of the carer. This can include home visits, virtual or phone check-ins, advocacy, and liaising with other agencies on the carer’s behalf.
Why <i>Describe any rationale, theory, or goal of the elements essential to the intervention.</i>	Kinship carers have a range of vulnerabilities and the children they care for have often had adverse childhood experiences. Kinship Connected aims to address the needs of carers and, by extension, the children they care for. A completed logic model, based on Kinship Connected’s Theory of Change, can be found in Figure 1 below.
Materials <i>Describe any physical or information materials used in the intervention, including those provided to participants or used in intervention delivery or in training of intervention providers. Provide information on where the materials can be accessed (such as online appendix, URL).</i>	In addition to practical and emotional one-to-one support and peer support groups (see below), the following materials or services are offered by Kinship to all Kinship Connected participants: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Confidential, non-judgemental and free advice service ● Someone Like Me telephone peer-to-peer support ● Applications for free or subsidised holidays ● Family events and Kinship Care Week activities ● Networking and support via social media.
Procedures <i>Describe each of the procedures, activities, and/or processes used</i>	One-to-one support from a dedicated project worker, usually for up to six months, includes:

¹ bmj.com/content/348/bmj.g1687

in the intervention, including any enabling or support activities.

- **Initial registration:** An in-depth assessment of kinship families' needs and circumstances. This includes the *Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Wellbeing Scale* (WEMWBS) with kinship carers: WEMWBS is a recognised tool for assessing population mental health. Project workers work with the kinship carer to set the goals they wish to achieve, and determine their 'priority' level – high, medium or low. High priority carers may require intensive support three times a week whilst lower priority carers may need more 'light touch' support. The aim is for carers to move through these priority levels, building resilience and self-confidence.
- **Three-month review:** An opportunity to assess where the kinship carer is with their goal objectives and to understand what further support is needed, if any.
- **Final six-month review:** Kinship works with kinship carers that need substantive support, over a six-month period, after which set goals have typically been achieved, WEMWBS scores have improved and carers can usually be assigned a lower priority level. When a kinship carer reaches low priority status, they will have developed new methods to support themselves and decrease dependency on services, and the case will be closed. They will continue to access other Kinship services.

Support can include advocacy, active listening, helping kinship carers access local and national grants, signposting to other agencies, family events, priority access to Kinship's advice line, confidence-building and skills development.

Peer support groups are a key part of Kinship's offer to carers. By taking part in a peer support group, carers' knowledge and expertise in relation to their own situation increases as does their confidence in their parenting skills (Starks and Whitley, 2020). Groups give carers an opportunity to share their stories, listen to each other, offer advice, and provide moral support. Some sessions are provided in response to demand, such as sessions on trauma and therapeutic parenting, which are delivered by Kinship project workers .

Project workers ensure that kinship carers can input into the co-design and co-production of the groups ensuring they work for them. This includes:

- Where the groups are held (online or virtual or a hybrid)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Topics discussed ● Guest speakers ● Making the groups sustainable, with training for kinship carers within the groups to step up and lead the groups.
<p>Who <i>For each category of intervention provider (such as psychologist, nursing assistant), describe their expertise, background, and any specific training given.</i></p>	<p>Kinship project workers have expertise in:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Working with vulnerable families with multiple or complex needs ● The challenges kinship carers can face such as financial difficulties, identity, older people's needs, disability, and long-term health conditions ● Legislation, policies, and practice that impact kinship carers ● Building high quality relationships with families ● Setting up, facilitating and developing support groups ● Managing projects or services ● Training or facilitating ● Multi-agency working ● Some have personal experience of kinship care. <p>Training and development for project workers includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Training policies and learning and development plans for every member of staff to enable personal and professional progression ● Monthly Lunch and Learn sessions where colleagues present on kinship care research, policy and practice issues ● Safeguarding: Received when staff begin their role, refresher training, issue-specific training, and local area training ● Database training: Using Salesforce case management system for impact. ● Reflective practice: A senior social worker conducts six weekly reflective sessions with all front-line staff to help reflect on their role, practice, and develop from these experiences ● Therapeutic support: An initial pilot with staff who are kinship carers, providing person-centred support from an independent specialist to enable staff to reflect on and process some of the cases they are working on, enabling them to feel better able to support kinship carers.
<p>How <i>Describe the modes of delivery (such as face-to-face or by some other mechanism, such as internet or telephone) of the</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Face-to-face individual support ● Volunteer-led peer support groups for kinship carers (virtual and in-person) ● Kinship carers also have access to in-person family events three times per year, telephone

<i>intervention and whether it was provided individually or in a group.</i>	peer-to-peer support and online networking and support via social media.
Where Describe the type(s) of location(s) where the intervention occurs, including any necessary infrastructure or relevant features.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Individual face-to-face support is provided in carers' homes or where needed (for example, accompanying carers and children to school meetings) ● Peer support groups are held in community venues, such as church halls or cafes, or virtually.
When and how much <i>Describe the number of times the intervention was delivered and over what period of time including the number of sessions, their schedule, and their duration, intensity or dose.</i>	<p>One-to-one support lasts six months, with some scope to work for longer in cases where this is needed. It can vary in its intensity: three times per week for designated "high" need cases, or once a week or less for "low" priority ones.</p> <p>Incidence of peer support groups varies, as they are run locally. Typically, groups meet weekly or monthly.</p> <p>Other activities are provided on an ad hoc basis.</p>
<p>Tailoring / how well <i>If the intervention was planned to be personalised, titrated or adapted, then describe what, why, when and how.</i></p> <p><i>If intervention adherence or fidelity was assessed, describe how and by whom, and if any strategies were used to maintain or improve fidelity, describe them, and describe the extent to which the intervention was delivered as planned.</i></p>	<p>Although its programme of support is consistent across England and Wales, local authorities can implement their own preferences. For example, some local authorities encourage self-referrals to the programme, whilst others act as a gateway for referrals, preferring referrals to come directly from social work teams. Other local authorities only allow referrals of kinship carers that have a Special Guardianship Order, though Kinship encourages an open programme for all kinship carers of children aged 0-18 regardless of background or the nature of their caring arrangements.</p>
Modifications (in the delivery for the study)	N/A

The Kinship Connected logic model, based on its Theory of Change, is detailed in Figure 1. Kinship Connected is designed to impact on children's mental health and wellbeing by ensuring kinship carers have the capacity to meet their kinship children's needs. The Theory of Change highlights that children's mental health outcomes are influenced by several key factors, including:

- Kinship carers being more able to manage children's behaviour
- Kinship carers feeling more able to manage family relationships
- Reduced financial concerns.

Figure 1: Kinship Connected logic model

Kinship’s other programmes² include:

- **Kinship Reach**, a remote one-to-one support programme, operating in nine local authority areas as of February 2023
- **Kinship Ready**, an online preparatory programme for new special guardians or those thinking about becoming one. As of February 2023, it is being delivered in 17 local authority areas across England and Wales. Six workshops over 12 months cover topics such as contact, trauma and attachment, support plans, overview of legal orders and where to go for help and support.

² kinship.org.uk/commission-our-services

Research questions

The pilot RCT aims to address the research question: **“Is it possible to conduct a full-scale RCT on the research question ‘Does the Kinship Connected intervention improve children’s mental health outcomes?’”**

To answer this question, the pilot RCT evaluation will address the following priority research questions.

Evidence of feasibility – Is it feasible to deliver the intervention and the study in a way that is acceptable to participants and Kinship staff?

1. Recruitment and retention:

- a. What are barriers and facilitators for recruitment?
- b. What is the expected recruitment rate?
- c. What are barriers and facilitators for retention?
- d. What is the expected retention rate?
- e. How to best recruit and retain a sufficiently large and representative study sample?
- f. What are appropriate incentives to maximise recruitment and retention?
- g. Are necessary recruitment and retention rates achievable?

2. Acceptability of the intervention:

- a. Is Kinship Connected as delivered for the pilot acceptable to Kinship staff?
- b. To kinship carers?
- c. What are the reasons people drop out of the intervention?

3. Fidelity and adaptation:

- a. How was the intervention delivered?
- b. Was the intervention delivered as intended (if applicable: with the required modifications)? I.e., were all activities delivered as planned?
- c. What variation was there in delivery across teams/sites?

Evidence of promise

4. Readiness of Kinship Connected for trial:

- a. Is there a clear description of Kinship Connected and the contextual facilitators and barriers that would allow it to be implemented and evaluated in other places?
- b. Is Kinship Connected able to be delivered consistently across teams?
- c. Are any changes needed to the theory, materials, or procedures before rollout?
- d. Ensuring consistent rollout: Are changes planned to the Theory of Change, materials, or procedures? Can they be completed before rollout or implemented after rolling out?

Ideally, the pilot RCT would also address the following research questions:

Evidence of feasibility – Is it feasible to deliver the intervention and the study in a way that is acceptable to participants and Kinship staff?

1. **Differentiation:**
 - a. What support exists for kinship carers in the local authorities that have been chosen for the intervention?
 - b. How is this similar to or different from Kinship Connected?
2. **Barriers and facilitators:**
 - a. What are barriers and facilitators for implementation?
3. **Reach:**
 - a. Did Kinship Connected reach its target audience?
 - b. What percentage of kinship carers did Kinship Connected reach in the local authorities that have been involved in the pilot?
4. **Acceptability of the study:**
 - a. Are all study processes such as the Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ) acceptable to Kinship staff and participants?
 - b. What are the reasons people drop out of the study?

Evidence of promise

5. **Mechanisms:**
 - a. Is there evidence to support or extend understanding of the Theory of Change?
 - b. Are there circumstances on the local authority side under which the intervention works particularly well/not so well?
 - c. Are there particular groups of kinship carers for whom Kinship Connected works particularly well/not so well?
6. **Potential impact and unintended consequences:**
 - a. What potential impacts of Kinship Connected do kinship carers identify?
 - b. What potential impacts of Kinship Connected do staff identify?
 - c. What potential impacts of Kinship Connected does the local authority identify?
 - d. Do there appear to be any unintended consequences or negative effects? Either from the intervention or from the study? E.g., is there an increased use of/take up of local/national services?

Indicative evidence of impact

7. **Design:**
 - a. Has the randomisation been implemented successfully?
8. **Measurement and data quality:**
 - b. Is the SDQ the right outcome measure for this study?
 - c. Is there a consistent and acceptable way of completing the SDQ across participants? (E.g., in private vs. with Kinship staff support)
 - d. Is the data quality sufficient to progress to a full-scale impact evaluation study?
9. **Outcomes:**
 - e. Are there changes in outcomes that can be measured quantitatively?

Cost

10. What is the cost per child/family of delivering Kinship Connected?
11. What is the minimum cost-effective effect size?

Outcomes

Research question	Indicator	Method
<p>Evidence of feasibility</p> <p><i>Is it feasible to deliver the intervention and the study in a way that is acceptable to participants and Kinship staff?</i></p>	<p>Fidelity and adaptation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Task lists/log entries from different teams/sites 	Admin data
	<p>Differentiation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> What are elements of Kinship Connected that have been delivered, compared to other interventions available for kinship carers? 	Document review
	<p>Barriers and facilitators</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> What do Kinship staff perceive as barriers and facilitators to roll out and implementation? What experiences did local authorities have with roll out and implementation? 	<p>Interviews with carers</p> <p>Interviews with Kinship and local authority staff</p>
	<p>Recruitment and retention</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> What are Kinship staff's experiences with recruitment and retention? What are projective participants' main barriers for participation? Are the incentives working? How many kinship carers have been approached vs. how many agreed to take part in the study? Of those kinship carers who took part in the study, how many a) completed the study b) provided data at all measurement timepoints? How many kinship carers need to be approached to achieve the final sample needed for the pilot/full RCT? Why do participants drop out of a) the study b) the intervention? 	<p>Recruitment log</p> <p>Drop out interviews/ short questionnaire if possible</p>
	<p>Reach</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number and characteristics of cases teams have worked with (demographics/Child Protection/Child in Need status/legal order, if any) Pathway of referrals (self-referral vs. practitioner vs. local authority) 	<p>Case data</p> <p>Local authority data</p>

Research question	Indicator	Method
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What is the overall population of kinship carers in the local authority that Kinship Connected was rolled out to? ● Are cases representative of the overall population of kinship carers or is there over/underrepresentation of certain groups (e.g., due to informal arrangements, kinship carers may not be identified as such on local authority databases)? 	
	<p>Acceptability of the intervention</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Is Kinship Connected as delivered for the pilot acceptable to Kinship staff? ● Is Kinship Connected as delivered for the pilot acceptable to kinship carers? ● What are the reasons people drop out of the intervention? 	Kinship staff/carer/local authority interviews/ drop out interviews or questionnaires
	<p>Acceptability of the study</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Are all study processes (e.g., SDQ) acceptable to Kinship staff and participants? ● What are the reasons people drop out of the study? 	Kinship staff/carer/local authority interviews/ drop out interviews or questionnaires
<p>Evidence of promise</p> <p><i>What evidence is there that the intervention can be delivered consistently for the period of the trial and achieve positive outcomes?</i></p>	<p>Mechanisms</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Is there evidence to support or extend our understanding of the Theory of Change? ● Are there circumstances on the local authority side under which the intervention works particularly well/not so well? ● Are there particular groups of kinship carers for whom Kinship Connected works particularly well/not so well? 	Kinship staff/local authority interviews and desk review of local authority and case data
	<p>Potential impact and unintended consequences</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What potential impacts of Kinship Connected do the following stakeholders identify? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Participants ○ Staff ○ The local authority 	Kinship staff/local authority/ participant interviews/drop out interviews

Research question	Indicator	Method
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do there appear to be any unintended consequences or negative effects? Either from the intervention or from the study? E.g. is there an increased use of/take up of local/national services? 	Local authority data on service uptake
	<p>Readiness of Kinship Connected for trial</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is there a clear description of Kinship Connected and the contextual facilitators and barriers that would allow it to be implemented and evaluated in other places? Can Kinship Connected be delivered consistently across teams? Are any changes needed to the theory, materials, or procedures before rollout? Ensuring consistent rollout: Are changes planned to the theory of change, materials, or procedures? Can they be completed before rollout or implemented after rollout? 	<p>Desk review of Kinship training material for staff and carers</p> <p>Kinship leadership interviews</p>
<p>Indicative Evidence of Impact</p> <p><i>Is there initial evidence that the intervention can produce outcomes that are measurable with the SDQ?</i></p>	<p>Design</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Has the randomisation been implemented successfully? 	Kinship staff interview
	<p>Measurement and data quality</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is the SDQ the right outcome measure for this study? Is there a consistent and acceptable way of completing the SDQ across participants? (E.g., in private vs. with Kinship staff support) Is the data quality sufficient to progress to a full-scale impact evaluation study? 	Interviews with kinship staff, psychometric analysis of SDQ data
	<p>Outcomes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Are there changes in mental health outcomes that can be measured quantitatively? 	Data analysis
Cost	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What is the cost per child (or family) of delivering Kinship Connected? What is the minimum cost effective effect size? 	Value for money analysis, Kinship admin data

Methods

Sample selection and recruitment

Intended sample size – impact evaluation

- 60 young people across approximately five local authorities whose carers receive support from Kinship Connected (the treatment group)
- 60 young people across approximately five local authorities whose carers do not receive support from Kinship Connected (the control group).

The proposed study would be a pilot RCT with natural stepped wedge design (Figure 2) to take advantage of a staggered rollout of the programme. Local authorities seeking to commission Kinship Connected would be approached to take part in the study. The timing of commissioning would be randomised and baseline measurements would be taken from all participating local authorities before any intervention starts. Subsequently, local authorities would be randomly assigned to receive Kinship Connected, until all participating local authorities receive the intervention. We propose a five step process with a pair of local authorities randomised to receive Kinship Connected at each time point. To allow the commissioning process to occur we suggest two months between each step.

Figure 2. Stepped wedge design (illustrative purposes only)

Intended sample characteristics

Child aged 18 or under, in kinship care and eligible for support through Kinship Connected.

Recruitment procedures

Kinship staff will recruit new, eligible referrals to the study. Depending on the agreement with the local authority, kinship carers will be referred by local authorities, self-referrals or through internal referrals from other Kinship services. . Local authorities seeking to commission Kinship Connected would be identified or approached and consent to take part in the study. Ten such local authorities would be identified. Pairs of these local authorities would be randomised at two-monthly intervals to rollout the Kinship Connected intervention.

As is customary with RCTs, we propose incentives to support families to join the study with a £10 shopping voucher.

Recruitment material

The research team will provide local authorities with reproducible and detailed guidance and support to identify children via a randomised approach, and to share with the evaluation team via secure email or portal. This will include a site initiation visit to each of the estimated five local authorities involved, to explain to relevant staff the study and consent processes

required. For example, what forms to fill out and when and how to return them, keeping eligibility logs, etc. The initiation visits will be supported by a dedicated helpline to a named researcher for any follow-up queries or concerns. We expect questionnaires to be filled out as part of Kinship workers' existing visits with families. Supporting research participants via their workers, who have established a relationship with the family already, should reduce the burden on study participants and encourage recruitment and retention.

Informed written consent will be obtained from family members via Kinship before they participate in the research. Any requests for participation in the evaluation will be accompanied by an information sheet that will explain the purposes of the research, how their data will be used and their rights, including the right to withdraw and complain.

The research team will ensure recruitment material is accessible by writing them in plain English and having two rounds of review. For round one, one Kinship project worker will review the recruitment material in writing. All changes will be incorporated, then, for round two, the project worker will show the recruitment material to a kinship carer, who will review the material and feedback. The Kinship project worker will forward any comments and suggestions.

Data collection

Quantitative data collection

The research team would measure the mental health outcomes of the treatment and control groups over a 12-month period, using a questionnaire at a minimum of three points:

- Before the trial ('baseline')
- Six months after the trial has begun, to coincide with the end of Kinship Connected support
- After a further six months, to measure medium-term impact.

The outcome measure for the pilot RCT is a short survey including questions on kinship carers and their children's demographic background as well as the SDQ, linked by a participant ID number.

Initial estimates from Kinship forecast Kinship Connected to be rolled out in a further five local authorities, subject to funding, involving approximately 300 children and 200 kinship carers (approximately 60 children and 40 kinship carers per location). Families will be sampled to ensure adequate representation across a range of characteristics in their case files, including demographics, time in care and/or legal order (e.g., Special Guardianship Order), levels of previous support from Kinship or another organisation. Kinship staff will be equipped to manage practical considerations around engaging children and families in the research, gathering consent and supporting visit arrangements. The initiation visits will be supported by a dedicated helpline to a named researcher for any follow-up queries or concerns.

Qualitative data collection

Data source	Priority research questions				Further research questions							
	Recruitment and retention	Acceptability of the intervention	Fidelity and adaptation	Trial readiness	Differentiation	Barriers and facilitators	Reach	Acceptability of the study	Mechanisms	Potential impact and unintended consequences	Randomisation	Measurement and data quality
Document review			✓	✓	✓				✓	✓		✓
Kinship admin data	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓		
18 children and young people	✓					✓						
20 Kinship Connected staff and relevant local authority stakeholders		✓		✓		✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Young people as participatory researchers (optional)	✓	✓				✓		✓				
Partnership meetings						✓						
Drop out interviews	✓	✓						✓				

The qualitative data collection will involve documentary review and redacted case file audit; two waves of primary longitudinal, semi-structured qualitative research with families of 18 children and young people, 20 Kinship Connected staff and relevant local authority stakeholders (potentially supported by young people as participatory researchers); two waves of observations of partnership meetings. Dropout from the process evaluation will be mitigated through consistent contact via Kinship staff; any children that drop out will be replaced with a child of similar characteristics (based on likely dummy variables) from the 120 children in the wider quantitative sample. Our approach will also test whether a similar process evaluation can be undertaken in a full RCT, for example whether participants can be successfully recruited and retained at a sufficient rate.

Five Kinship Connected local authority areas will be involved in the study, all new local authorities joining the programme to test the roll-out of the intervention as would occur in other local authorities. Families will be sampled to ensure adequate representation across a range of characteristics including demographics, time in care and/or under a Special Guardianship Order (SGO), and levels of previous support from Kinship or other organisation. Kinship staff will be equipped (remotely) to manage practical considerations around engaging children and families in the research, gathering consent and supporting visit arrangements. The initiation visits will be supported by a dedicated helpline to a named researcher for any follow-up queries or concerns.

The research team will undertake an Equality Impact Assessment and COVID-19 risk assessment so that the study allows equality of opportunity to participate and removes any existing barriers. They will collect data to ensure adequate demographic representation and to understand the impact of COVID-19 restrictions on any primary research. The assessments should be informed by relevant guidance; for example, the INCLUDE Ethnicity Framework and general guidance from the Centre for Ethnic Health Research, the National Institute for Health and Care Research, Market Research Society and Social Research Association.

Analysis

A statistical analysis plan will be developed detailing the randomisation schedule, scoring of the questionnaires and a description of the analysis that will be run. Analysis will be undertaken using SPSS or R software based on descriptive and inferential analysis such as multi-level

modelling, clustered at local authority level. The analysis will be mostly descriptive. Key proportions (such as retention proportions) will be estimated alongside 95% confidence intervals, corrected for the randomisation. All findings will be linked to the study's aims and objectives relevant to the pilot RCT and the intervention's Theory of Change. The analysis will not be used to assess whether the programme is effective or not as it does not aim to test the intervention hypothesis, but will check data quality (e.g. missing values), attrition, power implications for the full RCT and analysis processes so that these are fit for purpose in any later RCT.

The results will be triangulated with the revised logic model, by looking for consistencies and inconsistencies between the different data sources.

Indicative evidence of impact analysis

Modelling will be conducted in line with what is proposed for the full-scale RCT; however p-values will not be interpreted. In particular, the standard deviation of the outcome variable will be estimated and reported. Analysis and visualisation scripts will be developed that can be recycled for full-trial evaluation.

Ethics

Ensuring this study is conducted to the highest ethical standards is particularly important given the nature of the client group involved and the potential need to randomise participants into treatment and comparator groups in any RCT.

The pilot RCT will adhere to relevant ethical frameworks and industry guidelines, including the UK Framework for Health and Social Care Research, the ESRC's framework for research ethics, and Market Research Society and Social Research Association codes of conduct. These include specific guidance on COVID-19 mitigation approaches and guidance on diversity and inclusion in research participation including guidance from the INCLUDE Ethnicity Framework, Centre for Ethnic Health Research and the NIHR. Risk assessments should be undertaken, particularly for fieldwork, to include Disclosure and Barring Service (DBS) checks and safeguards for lone working and COVID-19 (see Risks below).

The feasibility study will test proposed pilot RCT design against ethical requirements and considerations, including randomisation. The feasibility study will seek ethical approval from a relevant ethics body, such as the WWCS Research Ethics Committee.

All participants will be asked to give their informed consent to the study and will have the right to withdraw at any stage.

In addition, patient and public involvement in the study from kinship carers and kinship children should be facilitated throughout the study. This should include, but not be limited to, input at the inception phase and review of research tools and reporting outputs.

Data protection

Data will be collected, managed, and processed in accordance with legal obligations and industry best practice. Approaches to data management is included as part of established project management standards, including Data Protection Policy and Information Security Policy and accreditations such as the ISO 27001 Information Security Management standard, ISO 9001 Quality Management Standard and Cyber Essentials Plus certification. For the purpose of this project, the research team and delivery team will be Independent Data Controllers.

The research team should provide WWCS with any and all data protection documentation including, but not limited to, Data Protection Impact Assessments, Data Sharing

Agreements, Data Privacy Notices before data collection, and liaise with WWCS where any legislative non-compliance is found.

Lawful basis for processing the data is legitimate interest for societal benefit.

Categories of individuals	Categories of personal data	Categories of special category
Children and families	Contact details Demographic characteristics (gender, ethnicity, relationship to the child, health)	Mental health (SDQ) Ethnicity Religion
Kinship project workers	Contact details Demographic characteristics (gender, ethnicity)	-
Kinship leadership team	Contact details	-
Local authority stakeholders	Contact details	-

Personnel

This is subject to commissioning of the pilot study. Ecorys and the University of Exeter undertook a feasibility study which included drafting this protocol for the pilot RCT.

- Ecorys: James Whitley, james.whitley@ecorys.com
- University of Exeter: Professor Mark Kelson, m.j.kelson@exeter.ac.uk

Risks

This section outlines the anticipated risks that may arise and steps that will be taken to mitigate against these.

Risk	Likelihood/Impact	Mitigation
Stakeholders (e.g., Kinship management, project workers, local authorities) have competing demands or do not support study	Low / High	Allocate time to engaging stakeholders in research. Benefits of study as extension of funding to be outlined.
Restrictions as a result of COVID-19 affect the ability to conduct study	Low / Medium	COVID-19 risk assessment to be undertaken. If required, all of the work can be undertaken virtually.
Recruiting or retaining families is challenging	Medium / High	Planned for incentives for families. Establish strong relationship with Kinship, who know how to work with this group.
Children or kinship carers negatively affected by answering SDQ questions	Low / Medium	Families supported by project workers

Escalation into crisis in a control group family	Medium / Medium	Information and advice provided as a minimum to control group participants
Data loss or data breach	Low / High	Robust project and data management procedures, overseen by Data Protection Officer (DPO)

Timeline

	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Q11	Q12
INTERVENTION (KINSHIP CONNECTED) TASK												
Setup in new local authorities												
Delivery												
Keeping in Touch with treatment and comparator groups												
RESEARCH TASK												
Strand 1: Inception and project management												
Project inception												
Research tools design	○											
Study Steering Committee												
Project management and updates	○		○		○		○		○		○	
Strand 2: Scoping the pilot RCT												
Set up data collection tools												
Scope the treatment and comparison groups for the pilot RCT												
Strand 3: Pilot RCT												
Data management plan			○									
Ethical approvals												
Randomisation												
Recruitment												
Data collection												
Data entry												
Analysis												
Trial management												
Strand 4: Dissemination, outputs and anticipated impact												
Reporting					○							○
Dissemination						○						○
Data archiving												

○ = Output related to milestone

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